

The Experience of Sustainability – Applying Metadesign to Invite Emotions to Further the Design of Sustainable Futures

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Abstract

What is the experience of a carbon neutral society? How does it feel to wear a cradle-to-cradle garment? This paper explores how the experiential dimension can enrich the development and communication of sustainability. The authors argue that such an approach can reach where quantitative and abstract language cannot, and foster a deeper relationship with ethical and environmental concerns, thus inviting designers and their colleagues into new and richer idea territories as regards sustainable futures. A series of methods and tools are proposed, designed to promote multi-sensory, and emotive engagement with the sustainability imperative and tested in recent empirical research taking the form of creative workshops. The rationale behind, the operation and benefits of the approaches are introduced through three cases, representing the fashion and automotive industries and a current AHRC funded research project ‘Bench-marking Synergy Levels within Metadesign’, (Goldsmiths, University of London.)

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Introduction

The larger context of this paper is the sustainability imperative, and in particular the need for organisations to convert to more ethically and environmentally viable practices. The paper explores how using experiential approaches in communicating sustainability can invite brands – and individuals – to engage in urgent processes of adaptation.

For all the knowledge we possess about aspirational culture, about the need to reach people at an emotive level, and the need to focus on positive agency, in the main sustainability communications is devoid of experiential language. It asks us to be more energy efficient – using the term climate change to rally our efforts. However, what is the *experience* of carbon neutrality, the *feel* of zero waste to landfill, the *sensation* of biodegradability? These are abstract notions, scientific terms where the negative or the reduction is in focus, and which do little to evoke an image of an enhanced quality of life, a vision of a better society for the individual, and for the larger community on Earth.

“A social movement is not scientific, its articulation must be permeated throughout with declarations of values and values priorities - norms, rules, imperatives... Is not the value-laden, spontaneous and emotional realm of experience as genuine a source of knowledge of reality as mathematics and physics?” (Naess, 1989: 32)

The researchers argue that communication of sustainability must acknowledge the reality of experiential culture and transcend the fixation with quantitative language in order to inspire essential change. As designers, we know that few people make consumer decisions solely based on intellect and numbers. It follows that a successful implementation of more sustainable practices necessitates approaches that more directly address the senses. How might we then envisage the positive experience of a carbon neutral city; or bring out the intriguing stories of a cradle-to-cradle garment?

The paper draws upon empirical research where such experiential approaches were used to empower environmental improvement within and across a range of design disciplines. The main focus of this work was:

- To cultivate the ability to imagine sustainable future systems;
- To add richness to a situated sustainability discourse by honouring experiential modes of understanding; and
- To facilitate proactive dialogue across design disciplines and professional cultures.

The paper presents these experiential approaches through three cases, all centred on creative workshops that took place in the UK, Sweden and France between 2006 and 2008. The first case

is situated in the fashion industry's mass-market segment. (Tham, 2008) The second case represents consultancy with a key actor in the automotive industry. (Lundebye, 2006) Finally, the third case forms part of a study spanning across design disciplines and beyond, *Benchmarking Synergy Levels within Meta-Design*. (Wood, *et al.* 2007-2009)

The Fashion Industry - Lucky People Forecast

Context

Fashion, arguably the fastest layer of commerce (see e.g. Brand, 1999), capricious and ephemeral, makes for an interesting case to juxtapose with sustainability. Fashion operates mainly on a symbolic level; when a user discards a fashion item, it is not because it is materially dysfunctional but because it no longer communicates the 'right' message at a particular time and in a particular context. It is on an experiential and symbolic level that the garment has ceased to perform.

All stages of the fashion product's life cycle affect the environment, key factors being intense water, chemical and energy usage. Increasingly strategies are in place to address the unsustainability of fashion. However, such strategies, and the legislation they seek to comply with, are mainly targeted at the production and processing stages of the fashion product's life cycle. Therefore, although the emerging strategies constitute a gratifying development, they fail to challenge the very scale and speed of a fashion system, which currently depends upon churning out new collections at a constantly accelerating pace. In such a reality, incremental improvements are easily eaten up by 'the elephant in the room' – over-production and over-consumption.

Process

The above served a context for a study conducted by one of the authors in spring 2006. (Tham, 2008) The study formed part of a PhD project, *Lucky People Forecast - A systemic futures perspective on fashion and sustainability*, which spans fashion design, futures studies and sustainability. The aims of the study were fourfold:

- To acknowledge and celebrate the symbolic nature of fashion;
- To invite fashion industry professionals into discussions about sustainability through experiential and opportunity focused language and activities;
- To encourage discussions between different stakeholders in the fashion system – such as designers, buyers, environmental officers, media and users;
- To create new and more tactile images and narratives of sustainable futures.

To this end a series of workshops with mixed fashion industry stakeholders was set up in the UK and Sweden. A substantive research design phase preceded the workshops where methodological approaches were developed. These sought to cater to a range of cognitive styles, to embody and

support a paradigm of sustainability, and to imbue a language relevant to a fashion audience. They were informed by a) sustainability literacy (e.g. Birkeland, 2002; Brand, 1999; McDonough and Braungart, 2002; and Orr, 1992); b) Futures Studies (e.g. Sardar, 1999 and Slaughter, 2001), and c) the visual and emotive language of fashion, and such design research methods as the cultural probes approach (see e.g. Gaver, 2001).

Figure 1. Area of study and methodological approaches. (Tham, 2008)

The workshops, which comprised a range of activities from the analytical to the creative, culminated in the generation of scenarios for fashion – in the context of sustainability – in 2026. These scenarios initially focused on *desirable futures*. (See e.g. Masini, 1999) The scenarios built upon a shared mapping process where the individual’s respective values and dreams were brought out. The participants were encouraged to draw out experiential aspects such as “what does it feel like to design for this concept, or visit this shop?” and to bring them to life through visualisations. At the end of each session, the groups went through a process of modifying the concepts to *possible* and *probable futures*. Here concerns such as financial viability and operational logistics became further pronounced.

Figure 2. A group visualises an open source, DIY iPod. (Company A, 2006)

Outcomes

The scenario activity was put in place as an educational tool for an immediate implementation of basic design for sustainability principles, and to practice taking design thinking to a systemic level. Another aim was to generate alternatives to dystopian or abstract futures narratives. Yet, the results of the scenario task transcended its aims, some of its benefits being distinctly relatable to its emotive dimension.

The ten concepts of fashion in 2026 that were created during the course of the workshop series spanned from the more realistic to the fantastic and encompassed ingenious rental systems, bartering models, and a closer relationship between user and designer (an example of which is the idea for a DIY iPod illustrated above).

The key benefits of the experiential approaches taken in the study were that:

- The participants could move from a fragmented understanding of sustainability to one more holistic and nuanced;
- The scenario work vivified abstract concepts and situated them in the individual's everyday realities and personal dreams;
- The participants were invited into more strategic and systemic designer roles, and could appreciate design beyond product level, celebrating the symbolic nature of fashion in new ways;
- Because of the hands-on, yet free space for discussion that resulted from the experiential approaches, barriers between professional roles could be negotiated, which brought a sense of hope, such as when an environmental officer discovered a designer colleague's concern for environmental issues;

- The workshops fostered a new sense of community between disciplines and cultures as participants experienced that colleagues and peers shared or respected their value position.

“...it gave me hope... the environmental concern was more manifest than I had thought... I discovered that there was more than I had thought... amongst our designers as well... and I found [that] very interesting and exciting... we have discussed more afterwards as well, this very inspiration that they too felt... they have had this... in their thoughts but it doesn't perhaps express itself every day as clearly.” (CSR C, 2006: 4)

The Automotive Industry – Trèves D³

Context

The second case of this paper is set in the practical, commercial context of the automotive industry where design and innovation play an increasingly important role. Car manufacturers follow lifestyle-trends closely because the demographics of their consumers are constantly diversifying, and because in contemporary culture the ‘car’ transcends the mere need for mobility.

Technology driven, innovation in the automotive industry has primarily focused on performance, speed, security and comfort. However, with a general growing awareness of greenhouse emissions, alternative motors, and more eco-conscious driving are slowly being introduced.¹ Efforts regarding production methods in light of end-of-life treatment are also increasingly in place, while the less product centred, systemic approaches – such as car pools - to mobility have yet to reach the mass-audience.

The project *D³* (Design et le Développement Durable) was conducted by one of the authors together with a supplier for the international automotive industry, Trèves, Paris. (Lundebye, 2006) Trèves wished to explore how the organisation's in-house design team might respond to pressing environmental issues and new European legislation. Besides building capacity within the team of designers as regards more sustainable design methods, the organisation hoped the work would enable it not only to be at the forefront of a highly competitive sector, but also to honour its responsibilities to the UN's Global Compact, in particular the principles for environmental responsibility. (United Nations, 2000)

Process

Exploring sustainability from a design perspective necessitated a re-evaluation of the organisation's inherent culture of design, and its assumptions of environmental issues. Three key challenges were identified: a) the general disassociation from environmental concerns, as presented in the media; b) taking ownership of sustainability terminology; and c) the perceived gap between personal and professional motivations. From an organisational point of view,

While addressing sustainability concepts from within the automotive industry might initially appear paradoxical and impossible, the designers were empowered by the workshop. Situating the workshop in the future allowed the participants to stretch beyond their present context and presumptions and to address environmental concerns alongside a range of human needs and aspirations. The approach of defined polarities allowed a playful yet focused and nuanced exploration of the territories in between. Thus the scenario work offered pathways to opportunities – a positive perspective contrasting with the doom and gloom picture many of the participants had held in their minds initially.

The work generated a series of positive comments from the management of Trèves. The key benefits that were highlighted were:

- How the co-creative space, crossing normal team borders, afforded a new sense of engagement at both individual and a collective levels;
- How the scenario work allowed the bringing together of personal and professional values and skills, which generated a sense of empowerment;
- How the nuanced new design territories that emerged offered fresh perspectives on design and spurred concrete design solutions.

Benchmarking Synergy Levels within Meta-Design

Context

The third and last case of this paper has a wider scope and higher ambitions than the two former.² Again, its larger context is the sustainability imperative, and in particular the failure of eco-design to solve some of the key environmental concerns that humanity is facing.

Sustainability poses particular challenges on the design community and requires a re-evaluation of the scope and purpose of design itself.

Metadesign offers a promising perspective on design in the context of sustainability. It can be described as the design of design, and of particular interest here is its notion of expanding design from product to system level, and from the deliverer of fixed content to design as a seeding process.

“[Metadesign] entails a shift from the normative planning of “how things ought to be” to the poetic enterprise of “how things might be.” (Giaccardi, 2005)

A key aspect of the Benchmarking Synergy Levels within Metadesign project is that of seeking to nurture synergies between a variety of professional disciplines, including design, architecture, marketing, community building and education, thus encouraging a proactive knowledge ecology.

² *Benchmarking Synergy Levels within Metadesign* is an AHRC funded project to be completed in January 2009. Its principal investigator is Professor John Wood, of Goldsmiths, University of London, UK.

Synergy can be described as the condition where the whole is greater than the sum of the parts. One of the project's outcomes will be a set of guidelines and benchmarks for an auspicious flow of resources within and between organisations.

For the purposes of this paper, two dimensions of the project are of particular interest. Firstly, the underlying stance that fostering conditions for sustainable futures requisites an agility between a multitude of ways of learning, knowing and sharing knowledge. The notion of such an "extended epistemology" can be found in action oriented research. (See e.g. Heron and Reason, 2001)

"In co-operative inquiry we say that knowing will be more valid if these four ways of knowing are congruent with each other: if our experience, expressed through our stories and images, understood through theories which make sense to us, and [is] expressed in worthwhile actions in our lives." (Heron and Reason, 2001)

A second fundamental proposition of the project is that fostering conditions for sustainable futures necessitates a reframing of the impossible as unthinkable, which in turn can help us access new possibilities. (Wood, 2007) Such a shift in mindsets can allow us to imagine modes of being and doing that can support humanity long-term.

Over the course of the project several interventions, in the form of workshops and seminars, have been conducted. Through these, a wide set of tools have been developed, explored and tested. According to context and needs, the tools can be combined to accommodate processes at varying participative levels and of divergent or convergent modes. Here, one particular intervention of the project is described, a workshop that took place in February/March 2008 at Pines Calyx (Kent, UK), a site that represents a pioneering example of sustainable architecture.

Process

The purpose of this two day workshop was to pilot a set of tools, designed to foster conditions for synergy, in the context of a metadesign brief. This overall task focused on alternative means and interfaces of exchange. Ten designers of various disciplines and six design and sociology theoreticians participated in the workshop. Because of its richly experiential notions the activity featuring the *five levels of processing story-telling tool* is of special interest for this paper. This tool was designed to help a group process and synthesise their personal experiences of an event, and to create a shared map that could ground, inform and inspire further work. In this specific case the story-telling centred around two presentations that the group had been offered, both introducing theories and examples of exchange. In the half-hour session five levels of processing took place:

1. The experiential – 'what did I sense?'
2. The factual – 'what did I learn?'
3. The systemic – 'what connections can I make beyond the immediate context?'

The playful, yet structured mode of story-telling also facilitated the making explicit of personal and professional experiences. This aspect was of particular importance in building group cohesion and organisation as skills and motivations were drawn out at a deeper and more nuanced level than general reference to professional role. The task that followed benefited from the participants' shared experience of moving with agility between the factual and the imaginative. Finally, the reiterative process of story-telling brought out a series of metaphors particular to the group and context. These metaphors, spoken and drawn, proved invaluable in the formulating of ideas in the ensuing creative project.

Conclusions

The sustainability imperative – to nurture sound, indefinite interdependence between social, environmental and economical concerns – poses particular challenges on the designer community, as on individuals at large. The central role of design in a producer and consumer society, which at an alarming and accelerating pace overpowers the delicate balance of the natural system, calls its professionals to question their practices and even design's very being. The authors have argued that this crossroad demands a discourse focused on opportunities instead of barriers and a practice employing a wide range of skills and approaches, applied holistically. Here we have emphasised the value of bringing into the implementation of more sustainable strategies and practices the experiential dimension.

To this end the authors propose that the model of a triple bottom line (encompassing ethical, environmental and economical concerns), frequently used in sustainability communications is expanded with an extra dimension – the experiential. Design has long and comfortably resided in the horizontal spectrum of the model shown below. Ultimately a design company must deliver profit to its shareholders, which it does by ensuring a competitive user experience. Now, as we are seeking to support the most important of causes, the sustainability imperative – and include the vertical spectrum of ethical and environmental concerns in the design activity - it appears crucial that we use our unique means of qualifying, adding texture and inspiration to a proposition.

Figure 5. A quadruple bottom line. (Tham and Lundebye, 2008, adapted from Lundebye, 2004)

The cases described in this paper have shown that drawing upon both factual and emotional resources can foster conditions for shared and proactive learning across design disciplines and cultures. It can consolidate tacit and explicit experiences and skills and create engagement on both personal and professional levels. It can help to vivify abstract concepts, and invite participants into more strategic and systemic designer roles.

“What imagination shows us is not arbitrary or merely subjective – it is part of the meaning of the object or experience. Thus, Kant says that the imagination enlarges the concept, opening up new significance in a creative generation of new structure and order.” (Johnson, 1987: 163)

In the commercial realm, the short-term perspective and the immediate context is systematically prioritised at the cost of sustaining the larger community long-term. However, increasingly the consideration of ethical and environmental dimensions is being perceived as a business opportunity instead of cost. Being hardwired in their views on time and efficiency and short-termist has resulted in companies not making time nor allocating budgets for ‘blue sky thinking’. However, cultivating the ability to imagine future systems and giving space to alter or enrich perceptions can create new opportunities and revenue streams within sustainable futures. Most importantly, engaging with the smell, the sound, the touch of the future – imagining its human qualities and thereby bringing it to life – situates the sustainability imperative in the personal and real domain and thus gives it a proper place in our collective plans and actions.

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